

Interview with Barrie Dale

Few scientists have had as profound an influence on the study of dinoflagellate cysts as **Barrie Dale**. From his first encounter with fossils as a child in England to his pioneering work at Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution in the 1960s, Dale's career has consistently bridged the worlds of geology and biology. In 1966, he achieved a milestone moment when he documented the first hatching of a dinoflagellate cyst, linking microfossils with their living planktonic stages—an achievement he likened to “hatching a dinosaur egg.” This discov-

ery transformed our understanding of the fossil record, harmful algal blooms (HABs), and the evolutionary resilience of dinoflagellates.

Over the decades, Dale's work has spanned continents and disciplines: from incubating cysts in seabed sediments to tracing their ecological signals in climate reconstructions and eutrophication studies. His contributions laid the foundation for modern HAB research, influenced international monitoring practices, and inspired generations of young scientists. His career

embodies the “golden era” of oceanography, when curiosity-driven science reshaped entire fields.

In this interview with **Kenneth Mertens**, Barrie Dale reflects on his formative years, the evolution of cyst research, and the lessons he hopes will guide the next generation of scientists. His story is one of persistence, interdisciplinary vision, and a lifelong passion for uncovering the hidden lives of some of the ocean's most remarkable microorganisms.

Personal and Career Background

What initially sparked your interest in dinoflagellate cysts?

Geology. As a seven-year-old I stumbled upon fossil roots from a 300-million-year-old Carboniferous tropical forest near my home in England, and from that day on I decided to become a paleontologist. I aimed for a geology degree, but fortunately I failed one of my A level GCE exams, chemistry, and that disrupted my university plans. Instead of retaking the exam, I seized an opportunity to follow an alternative as a research technician in Sheffield University's geology department, a global leader in organic-walled microfossils (palynology). I developed techniques to dissolve rocks and expose ancient acritarchs—microplankton fossils thought extinct. This work introduced me to graduate student David Wall, who as a Post Doc at the Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution (WHOI) later invited me to join him in the search for living representatives of these fossils, which turned out to be dinoflagellate cysts¹.

How did you first encounter dinoflagellates at Woods Hole?

In the early-1960s paleontologist Bill Evitt showed morphological evidence suggesting that some fossil acritarchs were dinoflagellate cysts [1]; a time when almost all biologists did not realize dinoflagellates produced such cysts.

¹ Editor's note: When Barrie Dale refers to cysts in this interview, he means resting cysts, which are often the result of sexual processes.

My role at WHOI was to help discover living representatives of these fossils in seabed sediments, develop incubation methods, and hatch them to reveal their planktonic stages. One night in 1966, I hatched and photographed for the first time the excystment of one of these, *Spiniferites bentorii*, a species linked to a Cretaceous genus, and it produced a swimming *Gonyaulax digitalis* ([2], Fig. 1). This was a transformative moment, akin to hatching a dinosaur egg in the Arizona desert. It and subsequent in-

cubation experiments confirmed that many acritarchs were dinoflagellate resting stages, linking geological and biological information for the group. The excitement seeing this first one hatch was a high point in my career.

Who were the key mentors and collaborators shaping your work?

At Sheffield, Roger Neves (Carboniferous spores/pollen) and Charles Downie (marine palynology) introduced me to microfossils. At WHOI, Charlie Yentsch

Fig. 1. First dinoflagellate cyst hatching documented at Woods Hole in 1966.

tutored me in oceanography, Bob Guillard in culturing techniques [3], and Bill Berggren, a foraminifera expert, kept me grounded in micropaleontology. David Wall was a pivotal collaborator, as PI for our projects discovering living cysts; I was his research assistant/associate [4]. In Oslo, Trygve Braarud, Grethe Hasle, and Karen Gaarder offered plankton expertise, patiently answering my questions and inspiring my biogeography focus.

Can you elaborate on the 1972 New England HAB outbreak?

The first major recorded *Alexandrium* bloom along the Massachusetts coast caused shellfish toxicity (PSP), leading to beach closures to shell-fishing. At this time Canada was monitoring *Alexandrium* along their East Coast, following Mussel toxicity issues affecting troop rations in WWII, and Maine had robust monitoring, using plankton samples and mouse tests to detect rising cell numbers and toxicity. This was the first report of PSP spreading down the coast to Massachusetts, and recurring blooms have been recorded since. Interestingly, despite much HAB research the cause remains unknown. David Wall obtained an outbreak sediment sample, and we hatched *Alexandrium* cysts with red eyespots, confirming their role in HABs. This event catalyzed modern HAB research globally, with funding eventually fueling toxic cyst studies. Political pressure from affected coastal communities (e.g., politicians' summer homes) amplified its significance.

Why did you relocate to Oslo, and what did you achieve there?

I considered the next step was to study cyst-plankton relationships, just how representative of plankton is the cyst record? David Wall was directing his research back to fossil cysts in the Jurassic and my suggested project was deemed unfundable in the U.S. The Oslo phytoplankton group with some of the longest interannual records generously invited me to join them in 1973 as a guest researcher to carry out my own project. Initially, I gave lectures at the four universities in Norway for a modest salary before applying for and securing funding from the Norwegian funding agency. In Dale, 1976 [5], I compared sediment cysts to several years of plankton data,

showing cysts represent multi-year plankton dynamics of approximately 20% of 55 plankton species. I greatly appreciated this opportunity to learn about living plankton ecology.

How did your early experiences influence your research philosophy?

My childhood fossil discovery instilled a sense of wonder about Earth's history and the details of the natural living world, shaping my research linking the two.

What role did the "golden era" of oceanography play in your work?

Post-WWII U.S. Navy funding aimed at "learning everything about the ocean", and this enabled our exploratory cyst research at WHOI in what Wally Broecker described in 1976 as "the golden era during which science was given a blank check by the public to pursue its whims" (Fig. 2). This freedom allowed us to pioneer hatching techniques and global distribution studies without immediate applied pressures, setting the stage for later HAB and environmental applications.

How did your role in HAB conferences shape the field?

I served on the Organizing Committees for many of the International HAB Meet-

ings and taught the first cyst workshop, at the Second of these in Florida, 1978. Some readers will happily remember a notable international conference, too, that I organized with the Sherkin Island Marine Station, Ireland, bringing together experts and young "experts-to-be" on HABs together with aquaculture interests, government agencies, and environmentalists in 1987 (Fig. 3). I always presented work at conferences, trying to bring a geological perspective to cysts in sediments.

How did your Oslo work build on WHOI findings?

At WHOI, we established cysts as living fossils and began to document their global distribution and ecological significance; in Oslo, I quantified how representative they are of ecology, showing cysts as reliable environmental indicators for paleoecology and HAB monitoring.

What personal impact did hatching the first cyst have on you?

I never "recovered" from the 1966 excystment of the first cyst [2] – it fueled my lifelong passion for sharing cyst research, driving my teaching and outreach efforts to inspire others in the field.

Fig. 2. Ready for decent on one of two of earliest dives for science with Alvin deep sea off US East Coast, early 70s.

Fig. 3. Barrie, Amy, and Karen Steidinger relaxing during the 3rd Sherkin International Conference on “The Problems of Toxic Dinoflagellate Blooms in Aquaculture, Sherkin Island, 1989.

What lessons from your career can guide future cyst researchers?

Embrace interdisciplinary learning, persist through setbacks, and prioritize sharing knowledge. My career path—redirected by a failed exam and enriched by global collaborations—shows the value of adaptability and community fellowship in advancing science.

Any final reflections on your career?

I’m deeply grateful for the Yasumoto Lifetime Achievement Award (HAB community) and the AASP Lifetime Achievement Award (paleontology), reflecting peer recognition for my efforts to bridge biology and geology. These honors are profoundly moving, affirming the value of interdisciplinary science.

Evolution of the Field and Research Challenges

What was your early work on cysts, and how did this help the field evolve?

At WHOI, we established for the first time that many cysts are dinoflagellate resting stages. We developed extraction and incubation methods, revealing well-preserved fossils and living forms. In 1968 we published the first paper linking living cysts to dinoflagellate phylogeny, and in 1977 we published the first ecological interpretations of global cyst distributions using FORTRAN punch-

cards and WHOI’s first computer in its own large room [6]. The 1972 New England *Alexandrium* HAB outbreak shifted focus to HAB cysts, and I published the first toxic *Alexandrium* cyst, from the Oslofjord [7]. Much of this work helped lay the groundwork for us and many others to develop the cysts into today’s substantial research field.

What do you consider your most significant contribution?

My work with David Wall at WHOI, particularly hatching and documenting the first cyst excystment in 1966, published in *Nature* as “living fossils”, was groundbreaking [2]. Together with co-authors, we discovered increased levels of toxicity in some *Alexandrium* cysts in Maine that could explain toxic shellfish in winter [8]. In Oslo, my students and I pioneered cysts as environmental indicators for eutrophication and pollution as significant tools for managing environmental degradation and recovery [14], and Amy Dale and I developed ecological models of recent cysts that proved successful for interpreting paleoecology back to Cretaceous Time in large biostratigraphic sequences ([9] shows a Paleocene example). On the personal level, I also include my efforts to help introduce many younger researchers to cysts through teaching workshops and seminars to research groups. I am proud to have helped some of the eminent scientists in the field today “find” cysts.

How has the study of dinoflagellate cysts evolved over your career?

Initially it focused on identifying cysts and their fossil status, the field expanded to global distributions, environmental applications, phylogeny (via molecular work), and applications in HABs, paleoceanography, and climate change. Early microscopy gave way to SEM, genetic barcoding, and AI-driven identification. Funding shifted from oil industry biostratigraphy to HAB research in the 1970s, then climate/paleoenvironmental studies were added, driven by societal priorities such as climate change. Anne de Vernal’s paleoceanographic models highlight the potential for cysts as climate proxies, despite challenges with quantitative accuracy. AI is revolutionizing taxonomy and cyst identification (e.g. a former student Robert Williams has digitized cyst slides with training programs to identify taxa [10]).

What challenges did you face in studying cysts?

Initially, moving to WHOI with no oceanographic training. These were fortunately the early days of modern oceanography – I don’t think there were oceanographic departments anywhere in universities, and the few oceanographers at WHOI were able and willing to help newcomers like me. Straddling biology and geology was demanding, requiring extensive literature review to include both. Institutional shifts, too: teaching marine geology while maintaining living cyst research in a phytoplankton department, or later the opposite challenges working in a geoscience department doubled my workload. Funding pressures increasingly favored applied research (HABs, climate, geo-industry), limiting basic science exploration. My research surely gained from dealing with such challenges.

What misconceptions about cysts persist in the scientific community?

Three stand out: (1) Cysts form primarily under adverse conditions—my evidence suggests they’re part of natural sexual cycles, often during population peaks when conditions are optimal; (2) All cyst morphology is functional—the incredible details of reflected morphology from thecae, for example, lack clear function; (3) Cysts form contractually inside thecal plates—development is

Fig. 4. Collecting sediment for a cyst survey of coastal waters of The United Arab Emirates for The Environment Agency, Abu Dhabi, 2011.

Scientific Aspects of Dinoflagellate Cysts

What environmental factors trigger cyst formation in dinoflagellates?

Lab studies suggest nutrient depletion or stress induces cysts, but natural triggers are less clear. Cysts likely form as part of sexual reproduction cycles, not solely in adversity. Field studies are needed to clarify how environmental factors interact with genetic and ecological drivers.

How do cysts contribute to harmful algal bloom (HAB) persistence?

Cysts anchor HAB species to a region, surviving in sediments for up to over a century, sometimes enabling recurrent blooms. For at least some species, cysts may be significantly more toxic than the motiles. However, blooms of known cyst-forming species don't always produce detectable cysts in the sedimentary record, as seen in an Abu Dhabi case (Dale & Dale, unpublished observations; Fig. 4), suggesting variable cyst production, resilience, or sampling challenges.

What is known about cyst dormancy and germination mechanisms?

Don Anderson and Jane Lewis' groups have provided foundational insights into dormancy and germination, but gaps remain, particularly for open-ocean species. Physiological triggers and survival mechanisms under extreme conditions (e.g., deep-sea pressure and low temperatures) are poorly understood.

Are there species with unique or surprising cyst dynamics?

Cosmopolitan species like *Protoceratium reticulatum* produce disproportionately high cyst numbers, aiding global distribution. Geologically, cysts enabled dinoflagellates to survive mass extinctions, highlighting their resilience and evolutionary significance.

Are there dinoflagellate species where cyst formation is not obligatory?

Yes, probably the majority. Particularly many open-ocean dinoflagellates likely rely on alternative survival strategies, as cyst formation is not universal.

more likely completed post-release, as seen in *Gonyaulax*, *Pentapharsodinium dalei* and *Lingulodinium* [13]. Literature with diagrams showing cysts with long processes inside complete thecae are misconceptions.

What are the biggest challenges facing cyst research today?

Funding is skewed heavily toward climate change and HABs, sidelining broader basic research. HAB prediction models have stalled, suggesting that a shift of emphasis to aquaculture monitoring is needed. Distinguishing details in environmental signals (e.g., eutrophication vs. climate) remains complex due to overlapping factors and sediment transport issues.

How do you see the future of cyst research evolving?

Funding will likely prioritize climate-driven research, potentially overshadowing other environmental issues such as pollution. HAB research momentum may decline as health-related funding for more pressing global crises competes. Promising areas include water quality bio-indicators, ballast water monitoring, and molecular/AI advancements, but basic science needs ever-more-protection from applied pressures.

Why is maintaining geo-bio connections important in cyst research?

The interplay between fossil records and living systems enriches our understanding of dinoflagellate evolution and ecology. Geological data provide deep-time context, while biological insights reveal modern dynamics, enabling more robust environmental reconstructions and predictions.

How do funding pressures affect cyst research today?

Climate and HAB priorities dominate funding, often at the expense of basic science such as cyst physiology or open-ocean dynamics. Researchers must balance societal demands with independent inquiry to preserve innovative discovery.

What makes dinoflagellates a "fantastic" group of organisms?

Single-celled yet exceptionally complex (eyes?), dinoflagellates exhibit diverse strategies—motility, predation, mixotrophy, and cyst formation—surviving extreme conditions and mass extinctions. Their evolutionary significance and ecological adaptability are awe-inspiring. There are probably few groups that can rival dinoflagellates for biological interest in the living and evolutionary potential of such a long and detailed fossil record.

How well do we understand cyst adaptations to extreme conditions?

We know little about how cysts survive conditions like prolonged darkness, high pressure, or near-freezing temperatures, especially in open oceans. Questions remain about sinking rates, floatation mechanisms, and density adaptations in deep water columns. Cyst formers in the open ocean must have alternative strategy than benthic resting stages.

How do cysts contribute to bloom forecasting?

Cysts indicate potential bloom initiation size but not bloom magnitude or fate, as water-column factors (e.g., currents, nutrients, predation, competition) dominate outcomes. The effective monitoring for HABs by John Hurst at the Maine Department of Marine Resources that I witnessed in the 1970s showed that it required almost daily plankton counts from strategic stations to follow a bloom for short term forecasting. It was not possible from counts in the initial population. Large cyst banks don't guarantee larger blooms, severely limiting long-term forecasting from cysts.

How reliable are cyst-based taxonomic classifications?

Morphological classifications are generally reliable when validated by genetics, despite some plasticity. Natural variation within species poses a greater identification challenge than plasticity itself.

What are the challenges in linking cysts to their motile counterparts?

Original descriptions often lack detail, and modern genetics/SEM reveal inadequacies. Creating new species names risks disconnecting from historical literature. I advocate re-sampling type localities to refine descriptions and maintain continuity. Also, the conflicts caused by "merging" geologically-based cyst species and biologically-based taxonomy are still avidly discussed after nearly sixty years.

How have molecular tools advanced cyst taxonomy?

Molecular analysis reveals genetic distinctions invisible morphologically, improving species delineation, and re-

vealing many new species. Barcoding enhances accuracy, though selecting appropriate genomic regions is critical for large dinoflagellate genomes. I hope they are using the appropriate ones.

Are there cryptic species distinguishable only by cyst morphology?

Likely, as seen in toxic/non-toxic *Alexandrium* strains, but identifying cryptic species in the wild is challenging without genetic confirmation. Morphological similarity complicates field studies.

How do environmental conditions influence cyst ornamentation and structure?

Salinity can alter process length, but effects vary within populations, suggesting internal genetic controls rather than uniform environmental impact. This variability complicates functional assumptions about ornamentation.

Can cyst morphology provide clues about evolutionary relationships?

Yes, fossil cyst morphology, when combined with genetics of living equivalents, supports phylogenetic reconstructions, showing good agreement with evolutionary patterns derived from living dinoflagellates. I think the close morphological similarity between living cysts and ancient "acritarchs" raises important questions for current research [17].

Are cysts indicators of harmful species?

Alexandrium cysts are notable, but morphology doesn't reliably indicate toxicity. Some toxic species may not form cysts, and others like *Pyrodinium* or *Lingulodinium* show variable toxicity, cautioning against generalizations.

Why are open-ocean cyst dynamics a research gap?

We lack knowledge about how cyst species of *Impagidinium* complete life cycles in deep water. Unclear sinking/floatation mechanisms and survival under extreme conditions highlight the need for sediment trap and molecular studies.

Applications, Implications, and Advice

How have cyst records contributed to understanding past climate change?

Cyst species tied to temperature-defined biogeographic zones serve as warm/cold climate indicators. Anne de Vernal's North Atlantic studies use cysts for paleoceanographic modeling, though sediment transport limits precise sea surface temperature (SST) reconstructions. I prefer the term "environmental signals" over quantitative proxies at this stage of understanding. I summarized cyst signals in Dale, 1996 [11].

Can cyst assemblages indicate past ocean productivity?

Yes, cysts of heterotrophic species dominate major upwelling/high nutrient zones now, signaling high productivity. Cysts of the more mixotrophic cosmopolitan *Lingulodinium* or *Protoceratium* dominate relaxation phases of upwelling off the California Coast and off large river plumes off Angola. These signals are also documented from older cored sediments.

What are significant climate reconstructions from cyst studies?

Examples include *Gymnodinium nolleri* appearing in the Skagerrak during the Medieval Warm Period (2,000 years ago) and receding in the Little Ice Age [12]. Karen Zonneveld described climate during Roman times in the Mediterranean. *Pyrodinium bahamense* records show global expansions during warming periods. Both warm and cold-water indicator species are identified from present-day cyst distributions, allowing their application as fossils for use in climate reconstructions from marine sediments analogous with fossil pollen in terrestrial studies.

How reliable are cyst-based reconstructions compared to other paleo-indicators?

Early transfer function models were statistically and ecologically challenged, especially for deep sea cyst records of predominantly coastal species. Coastal settings allow reliable signals if environmental conditions are stable, but

transport of the lighter cysts in open oceans complicates comparisons with foraminifera and other mineralized microfossils commonly used. However, the latter are subject to dissolution, especially at high latitudes whereas organic-walled cysts remain recoverable using palynology methods. This has increased the value of cysts as paleo-indicators in paleoceanography and deep geological applications. The use of best analogues from a global database is now preferred as a basis for cyst-based reconstructions, but the analogues still rely on the same assumed relationship between cysts and surface waters. The precision of reconstructions of actual sea surface temperatures and salinities using cyst proxies may still be challenged.

How do cysts inform past harmful algal blooms?

Cysts identify HAB species in sediments post-bloom, aiding “after-the fact” species identification in understudied regions. However, geological “bloom” evidence is often misinterpreted, as species dominance may reflect regular abundance, not a bloom event. Blooms cannot be unequivocally identified in the geological record.

Do cyst distribution patterns suggest climate-driven population shifts?

Yes, *Gymnodinium nolleri* and *Pyrodinium bahamense* records show climate-linked expansions and retreats, correlating with warming/cooling periods such as the Medieval Warm Period and Little Ice Age [12].

Can modern cyst deposition patterns predict future climate-driven changes?

Cyst records provide historical climate insights, suggesting future trends, but bloom prediction remains unreliable due to complex water-column dynamics. Past and present data together can provide important risk assessments for considering possible future climate-driven change.

How have human activities like eutrophication influenced cyst assemblages?

In the nutrient restricted Oslo Fjord, eutrophication doubled the amount of nutrients, and doubled the amounts of

Fig. 5. Barrie at home, 2019.

cysts, largely by providing extra nutrients to late-blooming *Lingulodinium* previously restricted to nutrients remaining after spring and summer depletion [14–16]. Industrial pollution reduced cyst numbers in another fjord, presumably due to adverse effects on phytoplankton. Eutrophication effects in another more polluted Japanese bay were associated with a shift towards heterotroph species, comparable to the natural upwelling signal. Studies investigating human impact should target sites to isolate one type of impact if possible – e.g. eutrophication with little or no industrial effects (clean-up efforts, as in Oslo Fjord, reverse these signals, offering encouraging feedback for environmental management).

How useful are cysts for ballast water monitoring and invasive species detection?

Cysts are critical for detecting invasive HAB species in ballast tanks, with proven success in identifying global transfer vectors. Regular sediment surveys enhance monitoring efforts. Comparisons between cysts in shipping harbor sediments and nearby unaffected zones help identify invasives, and cysts in well dated sediment cores help trace new introductions.

Can cyst DNA analysis improve HAB species detection?

Yes, DNA analysis distinguishes morphologically similar species such as in *Alexandrium*. Field-friendly kits could improve monitoring, but differentiating cyst-specific DNA from motile DNA in sediments is a challenge – we need confidence that motile DNA degenerates

rapidly if DNA is used for quantifying seed banks.

What are the most promising new techniques for studying cysts?

Single-cyst molecular analysis, genetic barcoding, and AI-driven identification offer improved precision and scalability for cyst research.

Are there cyst-based bio-indicators for water quality or ecosystem health?

Cysts show potential as water quality indicators, like EU benthic foraminifera standards. Cyst surveys for aquaculture site licensing and monitoring can detect toxic cysts and eutrophication effects.

How can AI or machine learning contribute to cyst identification?

AI, as demonstrated by Robert Williams [10], enables automated cyst identification and remote slide sharing among experts, mirroring pathology practices. This could revolutionize global cyst research collaboration.

What open questions remain about cysts in ecosystem resilience?

Most questions remain open, as cysts are one life stage of one group. Their ecosystem impact is limited but potentially significant, requiring humble acknowledgment of broader biological complexities.

How can cyst studies be integrated into global monitoring efforts?

Cyst surveys provide multi-year data from each sediment sample, complementing plankton sampling requiring many per year. This potentially adds monitoring possibilities for tracing global cyst-forming HAB species in sediment surveys investigating global change (chemical pollution, microplastic etc.). The cysts would also provide signals for other possible environmental changes if surveys continued for long-term monitoring. DNA-based monitoring should be standardized for aquaculture and environmental management.

What advice would you give early-career cyst researchers?

Explore dinoflagellates beyond HAB species or any other speciality, appreciating their diverse ecologic strategies.

HAB species are singled out primarily for their threat to humans – we need to know more about blooms as a phenomenon of phytoplankton generally to better understand HABs. Consider the history of geo-bio cyst research and value interdisciplinary connections. Remember we are paid to think. Resist funding pressures that stifle independent thought, share findings openly, and avoid exaggerating HAB impacts. Read enough to avoid “reinventing the wheel”. Commit to helping others to enter the field as you were helped and contribute to the good fellowship that fosters productive science. Enjoy the privileges a part in scientific endeavors brings.

If restarting your career, what aspect of cyst research would you focus on?

I'd delve into dinoflagellate phylogeny, exploring their possible evolutionary role between prokaryotes and eukaryotes, using cysts and protist biology as evidence. I think the close detailed morphological similarities between some ancient acritarchs and living cysts suggests a much longer geological history for the group, more in line with geochemical markers and molecular phylogenies than the current paleontological mantra [17].

How can cyst research support aquaculture?

Cyst surveys during aquaculture site licensing can detect toxic species, preventing HAB risks. Ongoing sediment monitoring tracks eutrophication-induced cyst beds, ensuring sustainable fish farming practices.

How do cysts compare to other microfossils as climate proxies?

Unlike foraminifera, cysts resist dissolution in northern oceans, making them valuable for paleoceanography. However, sediment transport complicates deep sea reconstructions based on the assumption that cysts on the seabed reflect conditions in directly lying surface waters.

Why is skepticism warranted for geological HAB evidence?

Fossil cyst dominance may reflect regular abundance in populations, not blooms. Environmental factors like droughts or gas leaks often explain mass mortality, not toxicity, urging cautious interpretation of past HABs.

How can researchers avoid exaggerating HAB importance?

Acknowledge that HABs are well-monitored in many badly affected regions,

posing less risk than many other health threats. Science has a responsibility to inform the public of state-of-the-art knowledge, for example stating the difference between known dangerously toxic species and those with traces of a chemical “poison” not known to adversely affect humans.

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Fig. 6. Grandad Barrie with his grandson Harald on home ground, 2024.